

Researcher Engagement & Data Group

2024 Annual Report

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Stephanie Thompson, Aslam Ghumra, Debbie Carter & Yajie Zhang

January 2025

Annual Report

2024

Introduction

The Researcher Engagement and Data Group (REDG) within Advanced Research Computing is comprised of 3.1FTE posts and engages with researchers across the University of Birmingham, from postgraduate level to senior academics, to ensure that they are aware of all the advanced computing facilities available to them through [BEAR services](#), as well as supporting their use through training workshops, 1:1 sessions and online learning materials. The team members are:

- Dr Stephanie Thompson – Researcher Engagement & Data Group Leader
- Aslam Ghumra – Research Data Management Specialist
- Debbie Carter – Research Training and Engagement Officer
- Yajie Zhang – Training Coordinator

1209

People engaged with us at events/inductions

Highlights of 2024

- Delivering the [Baskerville Showcase](#) to 65 attendees from across the country and overseas
- 54% increased response rate with the biennial [‘IT Needs of Active Research’ survey](#)
- The number of active users on our supercomputer, BlueBEAR, increased by nearly one third over the year to >3000 users
- Coordinating a [successful HPC Wire Award for Life Sciences](#)
- Hosting two year 11 [work experience students](#) and providing outreach experience for several others

197

People attended either a drop-in or 1:1 session

Collaborations within UoB

- The BEAR Champion voluntary group reached their 5th anniversary, with [five new BEAR Champions joining in 2024](#)
- The group met regularly, providing feedback on BEAR services and helping with training and outreach eg. setting up a new OpenFOAM and Julia Special Interest Group
- The 13th [BEAR Conference](#) successfully ran in April, featuring keynote speakers, live demos and PGRs describing a wide variety of research enabled by High Performance Computing
- REDG regularly met with the Library, Graduate School, and other researcher developer support staff
- Stephanie participated in the Open Research Board Operational Group, Mapping Research Enabler Roles Working Group (WG), and is a UoB Sustainability Champion
- Debbie participated in the IT Services People & Culture WG

Outreach

- We gave talks at 14 sessions to raise awareness and encourage use of services, including to College of Arts and Law researchers and at the [BioFAIR Roadshow](#)
- REDG attended 20 University events, engaging with over 1200 researchers. We also met with 197 people on a 1:1 basis to support them with using BEAR services – see Appendix

389

People attended our training workshops

623

New enrolments on our Canvas courses in 2024

11,831

Total page views of our blog posts

Training

- 9 different [training workshops](#) were delivered at regular intervals over the year with 31 workshops held in total (6 online) and 389 attendees
- 3 new workshops were developed and delivered – Advanced BlueBEAR, Image Processing with Python, and Introduction to R and RStudio
- Time is scheduled with Research Software Engineers and Research Data Scientists to deliver several more workshops throughout 2025, including Advanced R and Intermediate Research Software Development
- Satisfaction with training recorded in our survey was the highest since 2019, with 85 people giving an average score of 4.3/5 (compared to 3.1/5 in 2022)
- Average confidence in using Linux and BlueBEAR increased significantly after attending the relevant workshops from 1/5 (extremely unconfident) to 4/5 (somewhat confident)

Communications

- We wrote 56 blog posts and the number of page views increased by 60% compared to 2023, with the most popular posts being a [case study using BlueBEAR](#), and the [Graduate Systems Engineer vacancy](#)
- We were featured in emails to all University staff from the Vice Chancellor regarding the BEAR Challenge in July, and about HPC Wire Awards in the University Briefing in November
- Complementary new postcards and a banner were produced
- [18 case studies](#) were compiled and published on our blog

External outreach

- Two teams from the [BEAR Challenge](#) represented UoB at the [CIUK Cluster Challenge](#)
- We hosted ARCHER2 training on reproducible containers and MPI
- The team participated in the following Committees/Groups:
 - Aslam – DRI Retreat Organising Committee
 - Stephanie – HPC-SIG EDIA Working Group

Conclusion

This year we have increased our reach beyond the University through delivering the well-received Baskerville Showcase, and internally by increasing engagement with the biennial survey. We will use the results of the PVC for Research-sponsored survey of researcher needs to direct further expansion of our training workshops. It was great to host work experience for schoolchildren at various stages, and meet students via the BEAR Challenge, inspiring them to pursue a career in computing. The students showed great enthusiasm in research computing, and it is clear from their testimonials that they appreciated the experiences provided. From attending the [DRI Retreat](#), we have seen that we are ahead of many institutions in engaging with the research community but an area we can see increasing need in is the handling of sensitive data. With new research groups arriving via the 125th Anniversary scheme, we face increasingly complex data handling requirements, which may require new solutions. In the next year, we are hoping to reach new areas via bespoke sessions and training, particularly to provide support for digital humanities and beginner coders.

Appendix

Figure 1 The types of queries dealt with per college via 197 1:1 sessions held in 2024. Researchers from the college of LES had the most 1:1 queries (cf. EPS in 2023), storage (RDS) was the most common query from all colleges.

Colleges = MDS – Medical and Dental Sciences, COSS – Social Sciences, LES – Life & Environmental Sciences, EPS – Engineering and Physical Sciences, CAL – Arts and Law.

